

Embodying an Artificial Tail: Exploring Neural Adaptation to New Body Dynamics

Mamoru Ueda¹[0009-0008-0178-2020], Yoshikatsu Hayashi¹[0000-0002-9207-6322],
Toshiyuki Kondo²[0000-0001-8200-9276], and William Harwin¹[0000-0002-3928-3381]

¹ Biomedical Science and Biomedical Engineering, School of Biological Sciences, University of Reading, Whiteknights, Reading RG6 6AY, UK

² Department of Computer and Information Sciences, Graduate School of Engineering, Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology, Tokyo, Japan

Abstract. This study explores tool embodiment, where tools are seamlessly integrated into one's body schema. A robotic tail controlled via electromyography (EMG) from arm movements is being developed. The aim is to understand how the brain adapts to embody this artificial body part and investigate the underlying neural processes. Participants wear an electroencephalography (EEG) cap, EMG sensors, the robotic tail, and stand-on foot pressure sensors. They repeatedly move their arm, triggering tail motions. After an initial period, tail control accuracy reduces to 70%, creating a sensorimotor mismatch between expected and actual motion. The hypothesis is this mismatch induces neural adaptation, analyzed through EEG and event-related desynchronization (ERD). Increased alpha power during reduced accuracy is expected, suggesting heightened attentional demands and sensorimotor integration as adaptation occurs. Combining neural, muscular, and kinetic data elucidates mechanisms of motor control and adaptation to novel tools like the robotic tail.

Keywords: embodiment · feedback error learning · EEG · ERD · EMG

1 Introduction

In the context of highly skilled individuals, embodiment means that they have integrated their tools so seamlessly into their body's schema (the internal representation of one's body) that there is little distinction between their own physical self and the tools they use. In the paradigm of motor learning, for a given unknown environment or unknown/lost body dynamics, motor commands are generated in the motor cortex, and driving the body schema, the brain predicts the resulting body motion. The set of predictions will be compared against the proprioceptive and visual feedback from the body. The errors between the prediction and feedback will be used to adjust the body motion so that the errors decrease over time. In this feedback error learning, the cerebellum acts as a kind of "teacher" controller, maintaining an internal model of how our body should move to achieve a desired action. When we attempt a movement, the difference between the desired movement (from the cerebellum's internal model) and the actual movement we make is used as an "error signal." Our brain then uses this error signal to gradually update and improve the internal model in the cerebellum. With practice, the cerebellum's model

gets better at predicting the right motor commands to achieve the desired movement [1], [2]. We hypothesise that when using the tool, this principle of feedback error learning can work for the embodiment process of the tool, i.e., the kinematics/dynamics of the tool will be embedded into the body schema for the better prediction of the feedback signals. In this project, we aim to understand the process of embodiment, i.e., how the body dynamics can embody a new artificial body part which can enhance the body dynamics. To this end, we developed an artificial tail which can be attached to the body, and hack the brain-body loops by using the Electromyography (EMG) related to the arm motion to drive the robotic tail. More importantly, we will monitor the embodiment process. We expect that humans can embody the dynamics of the robotic tail in control of body posture. Specifically, as the robotic tail becomes a part of a whole body, the human will make postural adjustments with their core muscles or leg movements to counterbalance the tail's motion and maintain balance. Evolutionally speaking, by putting back the tail to humans, we will find out how the brain regains its function to control the tail in order to maintain a balanced posture. In the experiment, after some practice in controlling the robotic tail, the error signal will be increased by reducing control performance. In this moment, specific neurophysiological signals are expected to occur at the unconscious level. Substantial research has examined the behavioural and physiological responses when control accuracy is purposely decreased, such as through the introduction of external perturbations or altered feedback. However, fewer studies have explicitly investigated the corresponding changes in brain activity and neural correlates associated with these motor adaptation processes. A non-invasive brain-computer interface (BCI) enables direct brain-computer communication, via EEG on the scalp. EMG measures skeletal muscle electrical activity during contraction and relaxation, using surface electrodes to detect ionic currents from muscle fibre depolarization and repolarization. By employing foot pressure sensors, task-related pressure patterns are monitored as participants control their posture. EEG data will undergo frequency domain analysis to extract ERD, and correlations between the ERD, EMG data, and foot pressure data will be examined and discussed. This multi-modal approach, combining neural, muscular, and kinetic data, can provide a comprehensive understanding of the underlying processes involved in motor control and adaptation.

2 Method

In this experiment, we seek to recruit a minimum of 20 healthy participants. During the session, participants wear an 8-channel EEG cap with conductive gel. Additionally, EMG sensors be affixed to the major muscle groups of the right forearm. A robotic tail is attached to the participant's back. Floor-mounted pressure sensors, arranged in a 30cm x 10cm grid, track changes in the participant's centre of pressure. Participants lift and lower their right arm over a 5-6 second period, repeating this motion for 10 minutes. When EMG activity surpasses a predetermined threshold, indicating the participant has lifted their right arm, the tail moves rightward. After 100 seconds, the robotic tail's control accuracy deliberately decreases to 70%. Participants are not informed of this reduction in control performance. We analyze the difference between when the tail moved and when it didn't move. Offline EEG data analysis involves standard

preprocessing steps, including bandpass filtering (5-30 Hz), Notch filtering at 50 Hz, and independent component analysis to remove artefacts. Preprocessed EEG data then undergo frequency analysis using the Fast Fourier Transform to examine changes in Event-Related Desynchronization (ERD) patterns.

3 Result and Conclusion

Fig. 1. The standard deviations of FFT results for comfort and discomfort conditions. (sample rate 250 Hz, buffer size 2 sec, 95% overlap)

The power spectral density analysis shows increased brain activity across most frequency bands with 70% tail accuracy (the discomfort condition) compared with 100% tail accuracy (the comfort condition). The most notable difference is in the alpha frequency band (8-12 Hz), where the discomfort condition exhibits higher power (Fig. 1.). Increased alpha activity is typically associated with attentional processes and sensorimotor integration. The findings suggest that sensorimotor mismatch is associated with increased neural activity, particularly in the alpha band, reflecting enhanced attentional and sensorimotor processing demands. Further statistical analysis and correlations with subjective and behavioural data would be needed to draw more definitive conclusions.

Disclosure of Interests. the authors have no competing interests.

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